

A Study on Buying Behavior of Retailers at Sri Jayalakshmi Garments Dindugul

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ABSTRACT

This paper is based on the study of how a Consumer as an individual or as a groups or organizations select, buy, use and dispose ideas, goods and services to satisfy their needs and wants. Retailers buying behavior is the result of the attitudes, references, intentions, and decisions made by the customers in the market place before buying a product. The objective of this study is to find the level of retailer's satisfaction, to identify the most influencing factor of buying behavior of retailers and to identify relationship between socio – economic variables and retailers buying behavior towards Sri Jayalakshmi Garments. The descriptive type of research is used in this study. The primary and secondary data are used for this study. The tool used is chi – square test. The population size is 150 and the sample size is 100. The study was restricted only to Dindugul district.

KEYWORDS: Retailers, Buying Behavior, Socio – Economic Variables, Most Influencing Variables, Purchase Decision

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I. INTRODUCTION

Kotler (1994) defines that – consumer behavior is the study of how people buy, what they buy, when they buy and why they buy.

Walters (1974:7) defines consumer behavior as 'the process whereby individuals decide whether, what, when, where, how and from whom to purchase goods and services'.

According to Engel, Blackwell and Mansard, 'consumer behavior is the actions and decision processes of people who purchase goods and services for personal consumption'.

II. Review of literature

Saluja (2016) the purchase intension of consumers is influenced by attitude variable. Most of the consumer loves shopping with friends and families. They are influenced by the friends, family members, celebrities, magazines etc. some of the main criteria which affect the buying behavior are quality, comfort and brand. Even all the demographic factors like gender, age, occupation and monthly income don't have any impact on buying behavior of consumers towards fashion apparels.

Kumar (2015) this study provides some insights on factors that would be important in managing consumers satisfaction. Consumers are not only concerned with the merchandise, physical surroundings, promotional schemes but also with after sales service, environment and security arrangements. The findings of the study contribute to the

understanding of the consumer shopping behavior and their attitude and intension towards retail stores. A retailer must understand and know in detail, various factors that lead to shopping intension and attitude of the consumers.

Ahamed, Ravi (2016) consumer behavior with respect of their preferences, influencing factors, reason behind purchase is quite important from the side of branded players. It is found from the study that apparels manufactures should focus on manufacturing various varieties to consumers in terms of design, style, as well as color. The fashion loving person always prefer branded clothes, since they believe that right type of branded apparel can be available only in the exclusive showrooms and revealed that the irrespective of the age and education respondents are preferring at purchasing branded garments in order to gain self-respect in the society.

Shafi, Madhavaiah (2014) the apparel market is growing quickly. Hence, the need of era is to understand the consumer psyche and proceed accordingly, this experimental study examined the influence of demographic and consumer buying attributes which influence the apparel buyer decisions, results of the study revealed that reference group, promotion, store attributes, product attributes, income and occupation are the main dimension of apparel buying behavior, this shows that the apparel stores should give more importance to apparel buying attributes to attract and appeal the consumers, and also the promotional

programmer also should be done aggressively and appropriately. The apparel stores should furthermore come up with programmers concerning various reference groups, develop product attributes as well as store attributes through which they could easily and accurately attract the consumers and offer service according to their needs.

Maran, Badrinarayanan and Kumar the study reflects that income factor and purchase pattern of branded apparel product. According to the raking by customers, the quality factor prevails in the first position, color and design, comfort and style and price are securing successive ranks respectively. The expectation level and satisfaction level towards the types branded apparel were having positive relationship. Finally, it can be concluded that it is important to know the customers buying behavior process and customer's requirements property. The branded developer should develop and place the products accordingly to the customer and that will help in sustainable apparel products development as well as better business performance.

Kumar (2017) it is concluded that the consumers of Ludhiana district are more interested in buying fashion and branded apparel. Even though the consumer's income is restricted they still prefer to buy branded apparels and they are usually updated for new arrivals in fashion and brands. Even though the consumer income is less, they still want to look smart and up to date.

Prasad (2013) customers gave high priority for availability of latest designs, availability of options, shopping for middle class, convenience of pick and choice and family shopping under one roof. Customers gave low priority for advertisement and trust. The factors which affect buying behavior customers are shopping, social compliance and discounts, cost consciousness and value for money and merchandise convenience customers trust, choice, durability and longevity aspects of apparel quality.

Bharathi, Devamaindhan (2017) there emerges lot of scope to capture a bigger market share in the apparel category as people want more variety these days and are becoming more style conscious. Private labels have an ability to satisfy value conscious consumers. Today, the consumers are very demanding and are looking for more variety. Private labels aren't the sub - standard alternatives that they used to be a few years ago. This study examined the influence of demographic and consumer buying attributes which influence the apparel buyer decisions. The apparel stores should give more importance to buying attributes to attract and appeal to consumers, promotional program also should be done aggressively and appropriately in targeting the PBLs. The study conducted provides insights about consumer preference for private labels in this category. Income, price, quality, advertisement and familiarity is a

VI. Analysis and Interpretation

The frequency distribution of retailers profile based on the various socio - economic variables of retailers towards Sri Jayalakshmi Garments.

Table 1 shows frequency distribution of retailer's profile.

S. No	Retailers profile	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Male	56	56
	Female	44	44
	Total	100	100

major factor that determines private label purchases. one of the important psychological construct that determines private label purchase is vale consciousness.

Asif, kaushik (2017) with growing awareness and entrance of new comers, consumers are becoming brand conscious every day. The objective of the study was to study the most influencing of various factors affecting buying decision. Female's age between 26 - 35 years is the highest buyers of international branded apparels. Result also show that buyers prefer visiting malls in comparison to showrooms and multi - branded shops for the purpose of shopping. The main influencing factors for buying branded apparels are its aesthetics, family, peer pressure culture, social media and celebrity endorsement. The study also concludes that there is no relationship between the buyer's family size and choosing for promotional offer. Buyers of all categories prefer discount more than any other promotional offer.

Sreerekha, Kumar (2018) this study reveals the consumer behavior of Coimbatore people on their apparel purchase. The factors considered points out the relationship between respondents attitude on apparel purchase and manufacturers decision on apparel promotions. This study summarize the various factors influencing consumer buying behavior of Coimbatore people and their choice preference on various dress collections, their spending nature choice of location etc. The overall study reveals the consumer decision offer apparel purchase among their preference on apparel purchase at different occasion.

III. Objective of the study

1. To find the level of retailers satisfaction towards Sri Jayalakshmi Garments.
2. To identify relationship between socio-economic variables and retailers buying behavior towards Sri Jayalakshmi Garments.
3. To identify the factors influencing buying behavior of retailers at Sri Jayalakshmi Garments.

IV. Hypothesis of the study

H₀: There is no significant association between socio - economic variables and retailers buying behaviour at Sri Jayalakshmi Garments.

V. Research Methodology

A sample design is a definite plan for obtaining a sample from a given population, from which the sample is drawn. It is the technique or the procedure the researcher would adopt in selecting items for the sample. The sample for the study is 100. The sampling technique followed in the study is simple random sampling. This study includes both primary and secondary data. The primary data is collected by using questionnaire. The statistical tools used are percentage analysis and chi - square test.

2.	Age (in years)	Below 20	20	20
		20 - 30	33	33
		30 - 40	34	34
		40 - 50	8	8
		Above 50	5	5
		Total	100	100
3.	Family size	Upper class	20	20
		Upper middle class	35	35
		Upper lower class	25	25
		Working class	15	15
		Poor	5	5
		Total	100	100
4.	Occupation	Employed	47	47
		Unemployed	5	5
		Student	19	19
		Home - maker	24	24
		Retired	5	5
		Total	100	100
5.	Annual income	Less than Rs.2,00,000	18	18
		Rs.2,00,000 - Rs.4,00,000	36	36
		Rs.4,00,000 - Rs.6,00,000	25	25
		Rs.6,00,000 - Rs.10,00,000	15	15
		Above Rs.10,00,000	6	6
		Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The gender wise classification of the respondents in table 1 shows that there are 56 male respondents and 44 female respondents. The gender wise classification of the respondents in table 1 shows that the majority of the respondents belongs to the age group 30 - 40 years and followed by 20 - 30 years. The majority of 35% of respondents belong to the upper middle class of the family size. The majority of 47% respondents are employed. The majority of 36% of respondents belong to the annual income group of Rs.2,00,000 - Rs.4,00,000.

Table 2 shows whether there is significant association between gender and retailers buying behavior.

Gender	Retailers buying behavior			
	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Male	2	32	22	56
Female	0	25	19	44
Total	2	57	41	100

Since the calculated value of chi square is 1.663 and p value is 0.4353957 which is greater than 0.05. H_0 is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant association between gender and retailers buying behavior.

Table 3 shows whether there is significant association between age and retailers buying behavior.

Age	Retailers buying behavior			
	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Low	1	31	21	53
Moderate	1	18	15	34
High	0	8	5	13
Total	2	57	41	100

Since the calculated value of chi square is 0.705 and P value 0.95071 which is greater than 0.05, H_0 is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant association between age and retailers buying behavior.

Table 4 shows whether there is significant association between family size and retailers buying behavior.

Family size	Retailers buying behavior			
	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Low	0	35	17	52
Moderate	0	14	11	25
High	2	8	13	23
Total	2	57	41	100

Since the calculated value of chi square is 11.943 and P value is 0.0177802 which is lesser than 0.05, H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is significant association between family size and retailers buying behavior.

Table 5 shows whether there is significant association between occupation and retailers buying behavior.

Occupation	Retailers buying behaviour			
	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Low	2	26	22	50
Moderate	0	12	10	22
High	0	20	8	28
Total	2	58	40	100

Since the calculated value of chi square is 4.504 and the P value is 0.3427 which is greater than 0.05, H_0 is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant association between occupation and retailers buying behavior.

Table 6 shows whether there is significant association between annual income and retailers buying behavior.

Annual income	Retailers buying behavior			
	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Low	2	7	21	21
Moderate	0	14	25	25
High	0	36	18	54
Total	2	57	41	100

Since the calculated value of chi square is 12.641 and P value 0.013169 which is lesser than 0.05, H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is significant association between annual income and retailers buying behavior.

Table 7 shows the most influencing factor in buying behavior of retailers.

Retailers buying behavior		
Attributes	Frequency	Percentage
Inspiration	19	19
Quality	13	13
Brand behavior	18	18
Shopping behavior	19	19
Purchase decision	20	20
Impulsiveness	11	11
Total	100	100

Source: primary data

Purchase behavior with 20% is the most influencing factor in buying behavior of retailers and impulsiveness with 11% is the least influencing factor in buying behavior of retailers.

Chart 8 shows the level of retailer’s satisfaction towards Sri Jayalakshmi Garments.

From the above chart it shows that the effectiveness of retailer’s satisfaction in Sri Jayalakshmi Garments is high. It has a score of 66.65, which is in the high region.

Table 9 shows that from whom the retailers get inspiration to buy the cloths.

Inspiration		
Attributes	No of respondent	Percentage
Friends	28	28
Family	30	30
Celebrities	21	21
Magazines	11	11
Fashion blogs	10	10
Total	100	100

Sources: primary data

From the above table it is showed that 30% of respondent are getting inspiration from family.

Table 10 shows whether the quality of the product consistently improved

Quality of product consistently improved		
Opinion	No of respondent	Percentage
Strongly disagree	2	2
Disagree	7	7
Neutral	30	30
Agree	40	40
Strongly agree	21	21
Total	100	100

Sources: primary data

From the above table it is shown that 40% of respondent are agree that the quality of the product improved consistently.

VII. Findings

There are 56 male respondents and 44 female respondents. The majority of the respondents belong to the age group 30 – 40 years. The majority of 35% of respondents belong to the upper middle class of the family size. The majority of 47% respondents are employed. The majority of 36% of respondents belong to the annual income group of Rs.2,00,000 – Rs.4,00,000. There is no significant association between gender and retailers buying behavior. There is no significant association between age and retailers buying behavior. There is significant association between family size and retailers buying behavior. There is no significant association between occupation and retailers buying behavior. There is significant association between annual income and retailers buying behavior. Purchase behavior with 20% is the most influencing factor in buying behavior of retailers and impulsiveness with 11% is the least influencing factor in buying behavior of retailers. 30% of respondent are getting inspiration from family. 40% of respondent are agree that the quality of the product improved consistently.

VIII. Suggestion

Provide offers and discount on the clothes during seasonal sales. I suggest to create own online website for selling clothes to consumers and earn more profit from it. Sell the products on seasonal basis. I suggest them to do advertise their products (cloths) in the market, so the consumer will come to know about the availability of the designer clothes in different location.

IX. Conclusion

This paper is based on the study of how a Consumer as an individual or as a groups or organizations select, buy, use and dispose ideas, goods and services to satisfy their needs and wants. Retailers buying behavior is the result of the attitudes, references, intentions, and decisions made by the customers in the market place before buying a product. From the above study it is observed that retailers buying behavior is affected by factors like socio – economic factor, psychological factor, cultural factor.

The study has been concluded at Sri Jayalakshmi Garments to know the retailers buying behavior in the company. The conclusion suggested to them is to provide offers and discount on the clothes during seasonal sales, to do advertise their products (cloths) in the market, so the consumer will come to know about the availability of the designer clothes in different location. The tools used for conclusion is percentage analysis and chi – square test, that there is no significant association between socio – economic variables and retailers buying behavior

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